

Mitochondrial and genetic biomarkers in tuberculosis: Treatment effects, adverse reactions, and immunosenescence

Version 1

Description

The dataset consists of DNA-based biomarker values from plasma samples of tuberculosis patients—specifically, circulating cell-free mitochondrial DNA and nuclear DNA levels measured after tuberculosis drug ingestion.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001

Researchers

Lauma Freimane (0000-0001-9391-6672)

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Mitochondrial and genetic biomarkers in tuberculosis: Treatment effects, adverse reactions, and immunosenescence

Description:

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

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Contact: Freimane Lauma (veidemane.lauma@gmail.com)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Restricted

Publication Date: 2025-07-30

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

To examine potential pathogen- and host-related biomarkers and assess their possible applicability in evaluating TB risk, as well as in predicting the consequences of infection and therapy.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To examine potential pathogen- and host-related biomarkers and assess their possible applicability in evaluating TB risk, as well as in predicting the consequences of infection and therapy.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Experimental data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- Others

.ddpcr, .q1p

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, I have, but the study setting did not allow for it.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data might be useful for future research into personalized medicine in tuberculosis, as well as for clinicians.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

No specific metadata standard will be used, but relevant contextual information (e.g., sample type, collection date, patient group, biomarker type) will be documented in a structured and consistent format.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The data can be obtained through personal communication with the author. Once received, the data can be accessed and analyzed using standard software tools such as Microsoft Office and an internet connection.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-07-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

There are no expenses, as the data is already freely accessible and FAIR.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Lauma Freimane (0000-0001-9391-6672)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Yes, data collection and sharing are subject to ethical restrictions if patients have not provided consent for the use and sharing of their data or biological material.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

- Privacy policies

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